

A Review of Biotic Interactions and Taxon Names Found in ibartomeus/OBServData hash://md5/35b1210f8b22088babe73b2b9012c15e

by Nomer, Elton and Preston, three naive review bots
review@globalbioticinteractions.org
<https://globalbioticinteractions.org/contribute>
<https://github.com/ibartomeus/OBServData/issues>

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Abstract

Life on Earth is sustained by complex interactions between organisms and their environment. These biotic interactions can be captured in datasets and published digitally. We present a review and archiving process for such an openly accessible digital interactions dataset of known origin and discuss its outcome. The dataset under review, named ibartomeus/OBServData, has fingerprint hash://md5/35b1210f8b22088babe73b2b9012c15e, is 77.2MiB in size and contains 54,191 interaction with 1 unique type of association (e.g., pollinatedBy) between 46 primary taxa (e.g., *Malus domestica*) and 2,961 associated taxon (e.g., *Apis mellifera*). This report includes detailed summaries of interaction data, a taxonomic review from multiple catalogs, and an archived version of the dataset from which the reviews are derived.

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Introduction

Data Review and Archive

Data review and archiving can be a time-consuming process, especially when done manually. This review report aims to help facilitate both activities. It automates the archiving of datasets, including Darwin Core archives, and is a citable backup of a version of the dataset. Additionally, an automatic review of species interaction claims made in the dataset is generated and registered with Global Biotic Interactions (J. H. Poelen, Simons, and Mungall 2014).

This review includes summary statistics about, and observations about, the dataset under review:

Allen-Perkins, Alfonso, Magrach, Ainhoa, Dainese, Matteo, Garibaldi, Lucas A., Kleijn, David, Rader, Romina, Reilly, James R., et al. 2022. “CropPol: A Dynamic, Open and Global Database on Crop Pollination.” *Ecology* 103(3): e3614. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ecy.3614>
<https://github.com/ibartomeus/OBServData/archive/8353d98c342da5365621056b16cf445a083c6f0a.zip>
 2025-04-19T07:28:15.108Z hash://md5/35b1210f8b22088babe73b2b9012c15e

For additional metadata related to this dataset, please visit <https://github.com/ibartomeus/OBServData> and inspect associated metadata files including, but not limited to, *README.md*, *eml.xml*, and/or *globi.json*.

Methods

The review is performed through programmatic scripts that leverage tools like Preston (Elliott et al. 2025), Elton (Kuhn, Poelen, and Leinweber 2025), Nomer (Salim and Poelen 2025), globinizer (J. Poelen, Seltmann, and Mietchen 2024) combined with third-party tools like `grep`, `mlr`, `tail` and `head`.

Table 1: Tools used in this review process

tool name	version
preston	0.10.1
elton	0.15.9
nomer	0.5.13
globinizer	0.4.0
mlr	6.0.0
jq	1.6
yq	4.25.3
pandoc	3.1.6.1

The review process can be described in the form of the script below ¹.

```
# get versioned copy of the dataset (size approx. 77.2MiB) under review
elton pull ibartomeus/ObservData

# generate review notes
elton review ibartomeus/ObservData\
> review.tsv

# export indexed interaction records
elton interactions ibartomeus/ObservData\
> interactions.tsv

# export names and align them with the Catalogue of Life using Nomer
elton names ibartomeus/ObservData\
| nomer append col\
> name-alignment.tsv
```

or visually, in a process diagram.

Figure 1: Review Process Overview

You can find a copy of the full review script at `check-data.sh`. See also GitHub and Codeberg.

¹Note that you have to first get the data (e.g., via `elton pull ibartomeus/ObservData`) before being able to generate reviews (e.g., `elton review ibartomeus/ObservData`), extract interaction claims (e.g., `elton interactions ibartomeus/ObservData`), or list taxonomic names (e.g., `elton names ibartomeus/ObservData`)

Results

In the following sections, the results of the review are summarized ². Then, links to the detailed review reports are provided.

Files

The following files are produced in this review:

filename	description
biblio.bib	list of bibliographic reference of this review
check-dataset.sh	data review workflow/process as expressed in a bash script
data.zip	a versioned Preston (Elliott et al. 2025) archive of the data under review
HEAD	the digital signature of the data under review
index.docx	review in MS Word format
index.html	review in HTML format
index.md	review in Pandoc markdown format
index.pdf	review in PDF format
indexed-citations.csv.gz	list of distinct reference citations for reviewed species interaction claims in gzipped comma-separated values file format
indexed-citations.html.gz	list of distinct reference citations for reviewed species interactions claims in gzipped html file format
indexed-citations.tsv.gz	list of distinct reference citations for reviewed species interaction claims in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-interactions-col-family-col-family.svg	network diagram showing the taxon family to taxon family interaction claims in the dataset under review as interpreted by the Catalogue of Life via Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024)

²Disclaimer: The results in this review should be considered friendly, yet naive, notes from an unsophisticated robot. Please keep that in mind when considering the review results.

filename	description
indexed-interactions-col-kingdom-col-kingdom.svg	network diagram showing the taxon kingdom to taxon kingdom interaction claims in the dataset under review as interpreted by the Catalogue of Life via Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024)
indexed-interactions.csv.gz	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-interactions.html.gz	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped html format
indexed-interactions.tsv.gz	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-interactions-sample.csv	list of species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-interactions-sample.html	first 500 species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in html format
indexed-interactions-sample.tsv	first 500 species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in tab-separated values format
indexed-names.csv.gz	taxonomic names indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in gzipped html format
indexed-names.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-col.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Catalogue of Life as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-col.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Catalogue of Life as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-col.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Catalogue of Life as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-discoverlife.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Discover Life bee species checklist as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-discoverlife.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Discover Life bee species checklist as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-discoverlife.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Discover Life bee species checklist as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-gbif.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with GBIF Backbone Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-gbif.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with GBIF Backbone Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-gbif.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with GBIF Backbone Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-itis.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-itis.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-itis.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-mdd.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Mammal Diversity Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-mdd.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Mammal Diversity Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-mdd.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Mammal Diversity Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-ncbi.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the NCBI Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-ncbi.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the NCBI Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-ncbi.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the NCBI Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-pbdb.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Paleobiology Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-pbdb.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Paleobiology Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-pbdb.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Paleobiology Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-tpt.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Terrestrial Parasite Tracker (TPT) Taxonomic Resource as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-tpt.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Terrestrial Parasite Tracker (TPT) Taxonomic Resource as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-tpt.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Terrestrial Parasite Tracker (TPT) Taxonomic Resource as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-wfo.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World of Flora Online as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-wfo.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World of Flora Online as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-wfo.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World of Flora Online as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-worms.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-worms.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-worms.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-sample.csv	first 500 taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in comma-separated values format
indexed-names-sample.html	first 500 taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in html format
indexed-names-sample.tsv	first 500 taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in tab-separated values format
interaction.svg	diagram summarizing the data model used to index species interaction claims

filename	description
nanopub-sample.trig	first 500 species interaction claims as expressed in the nanopub format (Kuhn and Dumontier 2014)
nanopub.trig.gz	species interaction claims as expressed in the nanopub format (Kuhn and Dumontier 2014)
process.svg	diagram summarizing the data review processing workflow
prov.nq	origin of the dataset under review as expressed in rdf/nquads
review.csv.gz	review notes associated with the dataset under review in gzipped comma-separated values format
review.html.gz	review notes associated with the dataset under review in gzipped html format
review.tsv.gz	review notes associated with the dataset under review in gzipped tab-separated values format
review-sample.csv	first 500 review notes associated with the dataset under review in comma-separated values format
review-sample.html	first 500 review notes associated with the dataset under review in html format
review-sample.tsv	first 500 review notes associated with the dataset under review in tab-separated values format
review.svg	a review badge generated as part of the dataset review process
zenodo.json	metadata of this review expressed in Zenodo record metadata

Archived Dataset

Note that *data.zip* file in this archive contains the complete, unmodified archived dataset under review.

Biotic Interactions

In this review, biotic interactions (or biotic associations) are modeled as a primary (aka subject, source) organism interacting with an associate (aka object, target) organism. The dataset under review classified the primary/associate

Figure 2: Biotic Interaction Data Model

organisms with specific taxa. The primary and associate organisms The kind of interaction is documented as an interaction type.

The dataset under review, named `ibartomeus/ObservData`, has fingerprint hash://md5/35b1210f8b22088babe73b2b9012c15e, is 77.2MiB in size and contains 54,191 interaction with 1 unique type of association (e.g., `pollinatedBy`) between 46 primary taxa (e.g., *Malus domestica*) and 2,961 associated taxon (e.g., *Apis mellifera*).

An exhaustive list of indexed interaction claims can be found in gzipped csv and tsv archives. To facilitate discovery, a preview of claims available in the gzipped html page at `indexed-interactions.html.gz` are shown below.

The exhaustive list was used to create the following data summaries below.

Table 3: Sample of Indexed Interaction Claims

sourceTaxonName	interactionTypeNam	targetTaxonName	referenceCitation
Rubus idaeus	pollinatedBy	Bombus terrestris	Agustin Saez/CONICET (Universidad Nacional del Comahue)
Rubus idaeus	pollinatedBy	Apis mellifera	Agustin Saez/CONICET (Universidad Nacional del Comahue)
Rubus idaeus	pollinatedBy	Ruizanthedella mutabilis	Agustin Saez/CONICET (Universidad Nacional del Comahue)

sourceTaxonName	interactionTypeName	targetTaxonName	referenceCitation
Rubus idaeus	pollinatedBy	Ruizantheda proxima	Agustin Saez/CONICET (Universidad Nacional del Comahue)

Table 4: Most Frequently Mentioned Interaction Types (up to 20 most frequent)

interactionTypeName	count
pollinatedBy	54191

Table 5: Most Frequently Mentioned Primary Taxa (up to 20 most frequent)

sourceTaxonName	count
Malus domestica	17213
Brassica napus	6850
Allium porrum	4748
Citrullus lanatus	3504
Vaccinium macrocarpon	3150
Vaccinium corymbosum	3064
Helianthus annuus	2395
Fragaria x ananassa	2184
Coffea canephora	1194
Coffea arabica	1065
Vicia faba	1007
Prunus dulcis	773
Fagopyrum esculentum	678
Actinidia deliciosa	512
Gossypium hirsutum	491
Mangifera indica	448
Pyrus communis	445
Coffea arabica/robusta	439
Vaccinium meridionale	434

Table 6: Most Frequently Mentioned Associate Taxa (up to 20 most frequent)

targetTaxonName	count
Apis mellifera	8273
Apis_mellifera	1829
Bombus terrestris agg.	1351
Bombus_impatiens	1338
Bombus terrestris_agg.	810
Lasioglossum malachurum	754
Bombus lapidarius	691
Bombus_bimaculatus	598
Bombus_griseocollis	597
Andrena haemorrhhoa	537
Andrena flavipes	503
wild_bee_unknown	465
Bombus terrestris	463
Bombus_spp.	457
Bombus pascuorum	438
Bombus pratorum	415
Bombus impatiens	352
syrphids	330
syrphidae	317

Table 7: Most Frequent Interactions between Primary and Associate Taxa (up to 20 most frequent)

sourceTaxonName	interactionTypeName	targetTaxonName	count
Malus domestica	pollinatedBy	Apis mellifera	6127
Malus domestica	pollinatedBy	Bombus terrestris agg.	966
Malus domestica	pollinatedBy	Bombus terrestris_agg.	810
Vaccinium macrocarpon	pollinatedBy	Bombus_impatiens	780
Brassica napus	pollinatedBy	Apis_mellifera	660
Vaccinium macrocarpon	pollinatedBy	Bombus_bimaculatus	554
Vaccinium macrocarpon	pollinatedBy	Bombus_griseocollis	525
Malus domestica	pollinatedBy	Andrena haemorrhhoa	454
Citrullus lanatus	pollinatedBy	Apis_mellifera	452
Citrullus lanatus	pollinatedBy	wild_bee_unknown	447
Brassica napus	pollinatedBy	Apis mellifera	418
Citrullus lanatus	pollinatedBy	Bombus_impatiens	414
Malus domestica	pollinatedBy	Lasioglossum malachurum	374
Prunus dulcis	pollinatedBy	Apis mellifera	359
Vicia faba	pollinatedBy	syrphids	330

sourceTaxonName	interactionTypeName	targetTaxonName	count
Citrullus lanatus	pollinatedBy	Bombus_spp.	327
Malus domestica	pollinatedBy	Lasioglossum algericolellum	300
Coffea arabica/robusta	pollinatedBy	Apis	299
Fragaria x ananassa	pollinatedBy	Apis mellifera	288

Interaction Networks

The figures below provide a graph view on the dataset under review. The first shows a summary network on the kingdom level, and the second shows how interactions on the family level. It is important to note that both network graphs were first aligned taxonomically using the Catalogue of Life. Please refer to the original (or verbatim) taxonomic names for a more original view on the interaction data.

Figure 3: Interactions on taxonomic kingdom rank as interpreted by the Catalogue of Life download svg

You can download the indexed dataset under review at [indexed-interactions.csv.gz](#). A tab-separated file can be found at [indexed-interactions.tsv.gz](#)

Learn more about the structure of this download at GloBI website, by opening a GitHub issue, or by sending an email.

Another way to discover the dataset under review is by searching for it on the GloBI website.

Taxonomic Alignment

As part of the review, all names are aligned against various name catalogs (e.g., col, ncbi, discoverlife, gbif, itis, wfo, mdd, tpt, pbdb, and worms). These alignments can help review name usage or aid in selecting of a suitable taxonomic name resource.

Table 8: Sample of Name Alignments

providedName	relationName	resolvedCatalogName	resolvedName
Bees than apidae	NONE	col	Bees than apidae

providedName	relationName	resolvedCatalogName	resolvedName
Abax	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	NA	Abax
parallelepipedus			parallelepipedus
Abax	SYNONYM_OF	col	Abax pilleri
parallelepipedus			
Abeja abdomen	NONE	col	Abeja abdomen
naranja			naranja

Table 9: Distribution of Taxonomic Ranks of Aligned Names by Catalog. Names that were not aligned with a catalog are counted as NAs. So, the total number of unaligned names for a catalog will be listed in their NA row.

resolvedCatalogName	resolvedRank	count
col	NA	509
col	class	1
col	family	69
col	genus	162
col	order	13
col	species	1111
col	subclass	1
col	subfamily	4
col	subgenus	1
col	suborder	1
col	subspecies	11
col	superfamily	5
col	tribe	6
col	variety	1
discoverlife	NA	1132
discoverlife	species	751
gbif	NA	377
gbif	class	2
gbif	family	83
gbif	genus	189
gbif	order	13
gbif	species	1221
gbif	subspecies	11
gbif	variety	1
itis	NA	723
itis	class	1
itis	family	71
itis	genus	139
itis	infraorder	1

resolvedCatalogName	resolvedRank	count
itis	order	13
itis	species	905
itis	subclass	1
itis	subfamily	8
itis	suborder	7
itis	subspecies	4
itis	superfamily	5
itis	superorder	1
itis	tribe	4
mdd	NA	1882
ncbi	NA	583
ncbi	clade	1
ncbi	class	2
ncbi	cohort	1
ncbi	family	71
ncbi	genus	162
ncbi	infraorder	1
ncbi	order	13
ncbi	species	1017
ncbi	species group	1
ncbi	subfamily	9
ncbi	subgenus	20
ncbi	suborder	4
ncbi	subspecies	5
ncbi	superfamily	5
ncbi	tribe	5
pbdb	NA	1652
pbdb	class	2
pbdb	family	78
pbdb	genus	86
pbdb	infraclass	1
pbdb	order	14
pbdb	species	28
pbdb	subfamily	5
pbdb	suborder	7
pbdb	superfamily	5
pbdb	tribe	4
pbdb	unranked clade	2
tpt	NA	1881
tpt	species	1
wfo	NA	1829
wfo	genus	9
wfo	species	43
wfo	variety	1

resolvedCatalogName	resolvedRank	count
worms	NA	1716
worms	class	2
worms	family	57
worms	genus	52
worms	infraorder	1
worms	order	13
worms	species	36
worms	suborder	4
worms	superfamily	1

Table 10: Name relationship types per catalog. Name relationship type “NONE” means that a name was not recognized by the associated catalog. “SAME_AS” indicates either a “HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME” or “SYNONYM_OF” name relationship type. We recognize that “SYNONYM_OF” encompasses many types of nomenclatural synonymies (ICZN 1999) (e.g., junior synonym, senior synonyms).

resolvedCatalogName	relationName	count
col	NONE	631
col	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	2318
col	SYNONYM_OF	348
discoverlife	NONE	1969
discoverlife	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	967
discoverlife	SYNONYM_OF	322
discoverlife	HOMONYM_OF	94
gbif	NONE	474
gbif	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	2790
gbif	SYNONYM_OF	514
itis	NONE	882
itis	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	2069
itis	SYNONYM_OF	117
mdd	NONE	2998
ncbi	NONE	681
ncbi	SAME_AS	2423
ncbi	SYNONYM_OF	87
ncbi	COMMON_NAME_OF	1
pbdb	NONE	2196
pbdb	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	792
pbdb	SYNONYM_OF	21
tpt	NONE	2995
tpt	SYNONYM_OF	3

resolvedCatalogName	relationName	count
wfo	NONE	2879
wfo	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	54
wfo	SYNONYM_OF	69
wfo	HAS_UNCHECKED_NAME	15
worms	NONE	2376
worms	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	597
worms	SYNONYM_OF	39

Table 11: List of Available Name Alignment Reports

catalog name	alignment results
col	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
ncbi	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
discoverlife	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
gbif	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
itis	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
wfo	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
mdd	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
tpt	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
pbdb	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
worms	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)

Additional Reviews

Elton, Nomer, and other tools may have difficulties interpreting existing species interaction datasets. Or, they may misbehave, or otherwise show unexpected behavior. As part of the review process, detailed review notes are kept that document possibly misbehaving, or confused, review bots. An sample of review notes associated with this review can be found below.

Table 12: First few lines in the review notes.

reviewDate	reviewCommentType	reviewComment
2025-04-20T08:54:43Z	note	invalid date string [2000-2001]
2025-04-20T08:54:43Z	note	invalid date string [2000-2001]
2025-04-20T08:54:43Z	note	invalid date string [2000-2001]
2025-04-20T08:54:43Z	note	invalid date string [2000-2001]

In addition, you can find the most frequently occurring notes in the table below.

Table 13: Most frequently occurring review notes, if any.

reviewComment	count
found malformed doi [NA]	11818
found invalid location: [invalid (latitude, longitude) = (NA,NA)]	7373
target taxon name missing	3448
found malformed doi [In preparation]	1657

For additional information on review notes, please have a look at the first 500 Review Notes in html format or the download full gzipped csv or tsv archives.

GloBI Review Badge

As part of the review, a review badge is generated. This review badge can be included in webpages to indicate the review status of the dataset under review.

Figure 5: Picture of a GloBI Review Badge ³

Note that if the badge is green, no review notes were generated. If the badge is yellow, the review bots may need some help with interpreting the species interaction data.

GloBI Index Badge

If the dataset under review has been registered with GloBI, and has been successfully indexed by GloBI, the GloBI Index Status Badge will turn green. This means that the dataset under review was indexed by GloBI and is available through GloBI services and derived data products.

³Up-to-date status of the GloBI Review Badge can be retrieved from the GloBI Review Depot

Figure 6: Picture of a GloBI Index Badge ⁴

If you'd like to keep track of reviews or index status of the dataset under review, please visit GloBI's dataset index ⁵ for badge examples.

Discussion

This review and archive provides a means of creating citable versions of datasets that change frequently. This may be useful for dataset managers, including natural history collection data managers, as a backup archive of a shared Darwin Core archive. It also serves as a means of creating a trackable citation for the dataset in an automated way, while also including some information about the contents of the dataset.

This review aims to provide a perspective on the dataset to aid in understanding of species interaction claims discovered. However, it is important to note that this review does *not* assess the quality of the dataset. Instead, it serves as an indication of the open-ness⁶ and FAIRness (Wilkinson et al. 2016; Trekels et al. 2023) of the dataset: to perform this review, the data was likely openly available, **F**indable, **A**ccessible, **I**nteroperable and **R**eusable. The current Open-FAIR assessment is qualitative, and a more quantitative approach can be implemented with specified measurement units.

This report also showcases the reuse of machine-actionable (meta)data, something highly recommended by the FAIR Data Principles (Wilkinson et al. 2016). Making (meta)data machine-actionable enables more precise processing by computers, enabling even naive review bots like Nomer and Elton to interpret the data effectively. This capability is crucial for not just automating the generation of reports, but also for facilitating seamless data exchanges, promoting interoperability.

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⁴Up-to-date status of the GloBI Index Badge can be retrieved from GloBI's API

⁵At time of writing (2025-04-20) the version of the GloBI dataset index was available at <https://globalbioticinteractions.org/datasets>

⁶According to <http://opendefinition.org/>: "Open data is data that can be freely used, re-used and redistributed by anyone - subject only, at most, to the requirement to attribute and sharealike."

to <https://github.com/zygoballus> for helping improve the layout of the review tables.

Author contributions

Nomer was responsible for name alignments. Elton carried out dataset extraction, and generated the review notes. Preston tracked, versioned, and packaged, the dataset under review.

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